

1 **Comment on “Constraining tectonic uplift and advection**
2 **from the main drainage divide of a mountain belt” by C. He**
3 **et al.**

4 Feng Shi^{1,2}, Xibin Tan^{1,2*}

5 1 State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics, Institute of Geology, China

6 Earthquake Administration, Beijing, 100029

7 2 Shanxi Taiyuan Continental Rift Dynamics National Observation and Research

8 Station, Beijing, 100029

9 Corresponding author: Xibin Tan (tanxibin@ies.ac.cn)

10 He et al. (2021) combined numerical landscape evolution modeling and analytical
11 solutions to demonstrate that mountain asymmetry, determined by the location of the
12 main drainage divide, increases with increasing uplift gradient and advection velocity
13 gradient, which promotes a better understanding of the tectonic influence for the main
14 drainage divide. However, their analytical solution on the relationship between uplift
15 gradient and normalized divide location (Fig. 2e in He et al., 2021) is only applicable
16 when the conditions (the lower uplift rate of 0.5 mm/yr and mountain width of 50 km)
17 are met. As a result, their applications to the natural examples are questionable.

18 Assuming $U_1 = 1.0$ mm/yr and $M = 50$ km, we analyze the relationship between
19 uplift gradient and normalized divide location, based on He et al. (2021)’s Eqs. (7 & 8).

20 Assuming the same elevation of the base level at the opposite sides, we have a new
21 equation:

22
$$2D^{\frac{2-b}{2}} + \frac{4\lambda}{4-b}D^{\frac{4-b}{2}} = (2 + 100\lambda)(50 - D)^{\frac{2-b}{2}} - \frac{4\lambda}{4-b}(50 - D)^{\frac{4-b}{2}} \quad (1)$$

23 which is different from Eq. (9) in He et al., (2021). In case of $U_1 = 0$ mm/yr, we get an
 24 equation even without λ :

25
$$\frac{4}{4-b}D^{\frac{4-b}{2}} = 2M(M - D)^{\frac{2-b}{2}} - \frac{4}{4-b}(M - D)^{\frac{4-b}{2}} \quad (2)$$

26 Therefore, the analytical solution on the relationship between uplift gradient and
 27 normalized divide location will change, following one of the conditions (the lower
 28 uplift rate of 0.5 mm/yr and mountain width of 50 km) changes.

29 To examine the relationship between uplift gradient and normalized divide
 30 location, we conducted six numerical landscape evolution models. Each uplift gradient
 31 (0.01, 0.02, and 0.03 mm/yr/km) have two contrast modeling, with $U_1/U_2 = 0$ and U_1/U_2
 32 $= 0.5$, respectively. According to our numerical modeling, there is no stable relationship
 33 between uplift gradient and normalized divide location, when one of the above
 34 conditions is changed (Fig. 1). Instead, there might be a correlation between the ratio
 35 of uplift rate on two edges and normalized divide location (Fig. 1).

36 According to the above formula analysis and numerical modeling, we do not find
 37 a stable relationship between uplift gradient and normalized divide location. In
 38 consequence, the results from the application of analytical solution in He et al. (2021)'s
 39 Fig. 2e to the Wula Shan, Northeastern Sicily, and Southern Taiwan shall be
 40 reconsidered.

42

43 **Figure 1.** Topographies of asymmetric mountain range generated by the TTLEM (Campforts et al.,
44 2017) in response to a linear gradient in uplift rate from U_1 at the bottom edge to U_2 at the top edge.
45 Red dashed lines are the main drainage divides of mountain ranges. The run time of 100 Myr is
46 sufficient to attain a steady state in all cases. All the distances from the bottom edge to the top edge
47 are 50 km, and all the distances from the left edge to the right edge are 100 km. Note that, the divide
48 location is similar when they have the same U_1/U_2 , but much different when they have the same
49 uplift gradient.

50

51 References

52 Campforts, B., Schwanghart, W. & Govers, G. Accurate simulation of transient
53 landscape evolution by eliminating numerical diffusion: the TTLEM 1.0 model. *Earth*
54 *Surf. Dyn.* 5, 47–66 (2017).
55 He, C., Yang, C. J., Turowski, J. M., Rao, G., Roda-Boluda, D. C. & Yuan, X. P.
56 Constraining tectonic uplift and advection from the main drainage divide of a mountain
57 belt. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), 1-10 (2021).

58